

THE MOST ACCURATE EXPERIMENT REFUTING THE SPECIAL THEORY OF RELATIVITY

Doctor of Technical Sciences **Plyasovskikh Alexander Petrovich**
St. Petersburg State University of Civil Aviation,
St. Petersburg, Russia

Abstract. The special theory of relativity (SRT) is questioned by many scientists around the world. From 1999 to 2014 In Bottler, Colorado, scientists at the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) conducted what appears to be one of the most precise experiments in the history of physics, during which readings of some of the the most accurate clocks in the world, located in different parts of the globe at different latitudes. The experiment showed that, regardless of the latitude of the location of the 12 clocks that were observed, absolutely all clocks tick exactly the same way. This experiment irrefutably proves the fallacy of the conclusions of the special theory of relativity (SRT), according to which moving clocks go slower than stationary clocks.

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1. Introduction

The special theory of relativity (SRT) is still questioned by many scientists around the world [1-3].

In this regard, experimental verification of the reliability of various conclusions and provisions of SRT is relevant. This is due to the fact that the effects predicted by STR must be taken into account when developing navigation and surveillance systems in aviation and astronautics to improve the accuracy of these systems. Using an erroneous theory can lead to errors in the operation of these systems.

This paper talks about one of the most high-precision experiments in the entire history of physics, the results of which irrefutably prove the fallacy of the SRT conclusions about the slowdown of moving clocks compared to stationary clocks.

2. SRT on the course of clocks located at different latitudes of the globe

In the first paper on the special theory of relativity (SRT), which was published in 1905, Einstein writes: “ If at points *A* and *B* of system *K* a synchronously running clock is placed at rest and observed in the system at rest, and if the clock from point *A* is moved along a line, connecting it with *B* , towards the latter with speed *v*, then upon the arrival of these clocks in *B* they will no longer move synchronously with the clocks in *B*. A clock that moved from *A* to *B* lags behind the clock that was in *B* from the very beginning by a second $(1/2)t(v/c)^2$ (accurate to values of the fourth and higher orders), if *t* is the time during which the clock from *A* moved to *B*. It is immediately clear that this result is obtained when the clock moves from *A* to *B* along any broken line, and also when points *A* and *B* coincide.

If we accept that the result proven for a broken line is also true for a curve continuously changing its direction, then we obtain the following theorem.

If there are two synchronously running clocks at point A and we move one of them along a closed curve at a constant speed until they return to A (which will take, say, t seconds), then this clock, upon arrival at A , will lag behind the clock that remained motionless by $(1/2)t(v/c)^2$. From this we can conclude that a clock with a balancer, located at the earth's equator, should go somewhat slower than exactly the same clock placed at the pole, but otherwise placed in the same conditions" [4]. In the given formulas, c is the speed of light.

Let us explain what Einstein means.

According to SRT, moving clocks run slower than stationary clocks.

When a clock moves in a circle around the earth's axis, clocks located closer to the equator move at a higher linear speed than clocks located closer to the poles (Fig. 1). Clocks located at the equator have the highest linear speed.

The radius of the Earth at the equator is 6378 km, so a clock located at the equator, due to the rotation of the Earth, rushes at a speed exceeding the speed of sound, namely 463.82 m/sec (more than 1600 km/h). The speed of most civil aviation aircraft does not exceed a thousand km/h. A clock located at a pole does not have linear speed.

Rice. 1. SRT predicts: clock A runs slower than clock B, and clock B go slower than clock C due to the different speed of clock movement in a circle around the earth's axis.

NIST experiment refutes SRT: all clocks run **the same**

Therefore, according to SRT, clocks located closer to the equator, due to the higher speed of movement, should run slower than clocks located closer to the pole. Clock A, which is located on the equator, should run slower than clock B at mid-latitudes, and clocks B must go slower than clock C at the North Pole (Fig. 1).

Einstein gives a formula that allows you to calculate the amount of lag of a clock τ moving at a speed v compared to a stationary clock:

$$\tau = \frac{t}{2} \left(\frac{v}{c} \right)^2,$$

where t is the time period for observing the clock (a year, for example), expressed in seconds;
 c is the speed of light.

Calculations in accordance with SRT show that an atomic clock located at the equator, moving at a speed of 463.82 meters per second, should lag behind the same stationary clock located at the pole by approximately 37.7 microseconds in one year.

When Einstein developed STR, scientists of that time had instruments for measuring time that were very imperfect by modern standards, and they had no way to test experimentally whether Einstein was right.

However, the precision of modern atomic clocks is sufficient by a large margin to detect the slowing effect of the clocks at the equator, predicted by Einstein, compared to the clocks at the pole.

The error of modern frequency standards is less than one second per tens of millions of years. Over the course of a year, modern clocks will move no more than 30 nanoseconds (one nanosecond is one billionth of a second). This is approximately a thousand times less than the deviation of the clocks located at the equator from the clocks at the north pole calculated using SRT.

Thus, modern scientists have very accurate and perfect clocks, which make it possible to determine with sufficient accuracy how much faster or slower clocks are located at different points of the globe at different latitudes.

In other words, the accuracy of modern atomic clocks with a thousandfold margin is sufficient to confirm the effect predicted by SRT of the slowing down of clocks located at the equator (compared to clocks at the pole) due to their circular motion around the earth's axis.

3. An experiment by scientists at the National Institute of Standards and Technology NIST that refutes SRT

The experiment in question was conducted from November 1999 to October 2014. at the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) in Boulder, Colorado. During this experiment, scientists observed the progress of frequency standards used by leading metrologists at NIST, as well as in laboratories in the USA, France, Germany, Italy and the UK [5-7].

Observations of the 12 most accurate clocks in the world were carried out over more than 14 years. These clocks are located motionless at points at different latitudes of the globe, which move around the earth's axis with different linear speeds equal to

$$v = \cos \varphi R_3 \Omega,$$

where φ is the latitude of the clock location point;

R_3 – radius of the globe;

Ω – angular velocity of the Earth's rotation, rad/s.

During the experiment, it turned out that all the observed clocks ran exactly the same for 14 years, despite their different linear speeds around the Earth.

Over 14 years, the clock at the equator should lag behind the clock at the pole by 0.53 milliseconds.

Because Italy is located south of Germany, a clock located in Italy would have fallen behind a clock located in Germany by about 0.1 milliseconds (100 microseconds) over 14 years.

This is a very large value by modern standards, since the error of modern frequency standards is less than one second over tens of millions of years, over 14 years - less than a

microsecond (a hundred times less than what is required to detect clock lag). This amount of clock lag in Italy, if the lag had actually occurred, could easily be detected by modern atomic clocks.

NIST Scientists' Findings

The scientists who conducted the experiment conclude that the laws of physics remain unchanged over time (at least they remained unchanged during the 14-year experiment).

4. Results and discussion

4.1. The experimental results refute SRT

According to SRT, atomic clocks located closer to the equator should run slower than clocks located closer to the pole. The accuracy of modern frequency standards with a thousandfold margin is sufficient to detect the predicted SRT effect.

As a result of an experiment conducted by NIST scientists, it was found that high-precision clocks located motionless at different latitudes ran exactly the same over 14 years of continuous observation.

NIST experimenters conclude that the laws of physics remain unchanged over time. However, NIST experimenters did not pay attention to the fact that their experiment, in fact, refutes SRT, according to which clocks located at different latitudes should move at different speeds.

The results of the experiment proved with the highest degree of accuracy the fact that the movement of a clock does not affect its progress, and that a moving clock runs exactly the same as a stationary clock.

The results of the experiment reliably refute the special theory of relativity, according to which clocks moving at a faster speed should lag behind clocks moving at a slower speed.

4.2. On the necessity of the Theory of Aberration - the first alternative theory to SRT, confirmed experimentally

Due to the fact that the effects predicted by SRT need to be taken into account in navigation and surveillance systems in the aviation and space industries in order to increase the accuracy of these systems, it is necessary to develop an alternative theory to STR that does not contradict the results of the experiment of NIST scientists.

The author of this work developed the Theory of Aberration - the first alternative SRT theory, which was confirmed experimentally [1-3]. A popular scientific presentation of the Theory of Aberration can be found in [8-9].

The theory of aberration can be used in science instead of SRT, the reliability of which is refuted experimentally.

5. Conclusion

An experiment conducted by NIST scientists revealed that all clocks on Earth, despite the fact that they are located at different latitudes and therefore move at different linear speeds around the earth's axis due to the rotation of the Earth, go exactly the same. According to SRT, clocks located closer to the equator should run slower than clocks located closer to the poles.

A 14-year experiment refutes SRT with the highest accuracy.

To improve the accuracy of navigation and surveillance systems in aviation and astronautics, an alternative theory to STR is required that does not contradict experiments. Such a theory is the Theory of Aberration [1-3, 8-9].

Please send your comments and suggestions regarding this work by email. mail: al.plyasovskih@yandex.ru

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